

Selection of durum wheat lines under organic management - Preliminary results

Mario A. PAGNOTTA¹, Luca BONFIGLIOLI¹, Paola FORTE¹

¹Department of Agricultural and Forest Sciences (DAFNE), Tuscia University, Via S. C. de Lellis, snc, 01100 Viterbo, Italy

(✉) pagnotta@unitus.it

Organic cultivation has been increased over the last decades in whole Europe. Italy is among the five European countries with the largest acreage of organic farmland as well as among the five countries with more than 15% of agricultural land under organic management. Organic cultivation has several advantages such as decrease of soil erosion, decreased ecological impacts (*i.e.* biodiversity, nature conservation, water use efficiency, and environment), increased adaptiveness to climatic changes, but it has also some disadvantages which the most important is the reduced productivity. Genotypes under organic agriculture need a high phenotypic plasticity to adapt to different and changing climatic conditions, should be more tolerant to abiotic and biotic stresses, need a proper root system to enable efficient nutrient taking and therefore produce high enough yields with less/low input. Another important topic is salinity tolerance. More than 6% of the world surface is exposed to high salinity and drought risks, which are correlated and responsible for the decrease in agricultural land and crop production. Plants under salt stress suffer from two components of salt damage, *i.e.* osmotic stress and ion toxicity.

The H2020 project ECOBREED aims to select germplasm adapted to organic production. To fulfill this objective 72 durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) accessions were evaluated under organic management at the Tuscia University in Viterbo (latitude 42°25'7"68 N, longitude 12°6'34"20 E, altitude 300 m a.s.l.) in the 2018-2019 growing season. The accessions were chosen on the base of previous information and their potential for organic production. The germplasm included old varieties, local ecotypes, pre-breeding material and modern varieties. The accessions were characterized morpho-phenologically recording several characteristics such as the number of days to terminal spikelet, booting, stem elongation, heading, anthesis and grain filling. Moreover the following measurements were made: flag leaf width, flag leaf length, flag leaf area, plant height, spike dry weight at anthesis, biomass per shoot at anthesis, fertile floret number per spike at anthesis, spike length, spike index, number of spikelets per spike, number of grains per spike, number of grains per spikelet, grain yield per spike, spike fertility index, grain yield per square meter, number of grains per square meter, number of spikes per square meter, biomass per square meter, biomass per tiller, grain yield per tiller, 1000 grain weight, harvest index, chlorophyll content, grain protein, and gluten content. Some characteristics regarding the root system architecture were also recorded (*i.e.* root angle, depth, amount).

On the basis of the first year preliminary evaluation, 25 accessions out of the 72 screened accessions, were identified with positive yield and quality characteristics, tolerance to abiotic and biotic stresses, and variation in terms of phenological periods. Regarding phenology it should be noted that the accessions have shown different levels of precocity, but the ranking in terms of precocity is not the same across the different growth stages. Some accessions showed very fast juvenile growth while others have a faster development at later growth stages. This is of particular importance since nowadays, as a result of climate change, the environment is extremely erratic and it is important to grow germplasm with different precocity levels allowing to escape unpredictably periods of adverse conditions.

Experimental trials and molecular analyses were performed on the 25 accessions in order to identify genotypes tolerant to salt and drought stresses. We used molecular markers associated to genes and transcription factors (like TPS, DREB, WRKY, SOD, HKT) connected with metabolic pathways for salt tolerance, *i.e.* regulation mechanisms of osmoprotection and ion homeostasis. For drought tolerance molecular analyses were performed with markers (as GWM and WMS) associated with traits related to the root system. Data confirmed that marker WMS5 is linked to seminal root growth angle. Plants with deeper root systems are in general also earlier maturing while the ones with a more superficial root system seem to be later maturing. It should be also noted that the root system was different between the accessions of Central European origin and the ones from the Mediterranean area. Further evaluations in different locations and years are running to confirm the preliminary results.

Keywords

Drought stress · molecular marker · organic agriculture · root system architecture · salinity stress · *Triticum durum*

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Figure 1 Durum wheat accessions with contrasting root angles

Figure 2 Differences in phenological development of durum wheat accessions. BBCH growth stage was scored on 1st, 15th, 23rd and 30th April, and on 6th and 13th May (x-axis) in Viterbo, Italy

References

Alahmad S, El Hassouni K, Bassi FM, Dinglasan E, Youssef C, Quarry G, *et al.* (2019) A major root architecture QTL responding to water limitation in durum wheat. *Front Plant Sci* 10: 436. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2019.00436

El Hassouni K, Alahmad S, Belkadi B, Filali-Maltouf A, Hickey LT, Bassi FM (2018) Root system architecture and its association with yield under different water regimes in durum wheat. *Crop Sci* 58: 2331-2346. DOI: 10.2135/cropsci2018.01.0076

Isayenkov SV, Maathuis FJM (2019) Plant salinity stress: many unanswered questions remain. *Front Plant Sci* 10: 80. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2019.00080

Julkowska MM, Koevoets IT, Mol S, Hoefsloot H, Feron R, Tester MA, *et al.* (2017) Genetic components of root architecture remodeling in response to salt stress. *Plant Cell* 29: 3198-3213. DOI: 10.1105/tpc.16.00680

Mondini L, Nachit MM, Pagnotta MA (2015) Allelic variants in durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. var. *durum*) DREB genes conferring tolerance to abiotic stresses. *Mol Genet Genomics* 290: 531-544. DOI: 10.1007/s00438-014-0933-2

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Department für Nutzpflanzenwissenschaften
Universität für Bodenkultur Wien
Konrad Lorenz Str. 24
3430 Tulln an der Donau
Email: pflanzenzuechtung@boku.ac.at

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